
99. Searching for Dyson spheres

IN MY PREVIOUS ESSAY, I looked at Gaia's contribution to the search for additional examples of the curious lightcurve, discovered from Kepler photometry, of Boyajian's star. Some of the interest in this star arose because of the early inference that its apparent variability could be a manifestation of one specific type of 'techno-signature' originating from an alien civilisation.

In my essay after this, I will assemble some top-level ideas about the origin of life on Earth, the search for life on other worlds, and what our current failure to detect alien life forms, or signals or other signatures of alien civilisations, might be informing us about the 'Fermi Paradox', viz., if other civilisations exist, where are they?

Here I want to look at one specific search for other civilisations which is being assisted by Gaia: the search for so-called 'Dyson spheres'. But let me be clear that I am not attempting to review the ever-growing literature on the Search for Extraterrestrial Intelligence (SETI), or on the topic of Messaging Extraterrestrial Intelligence (METI): in what will hopefully become an annual review, and providing an excellent entry into the relevant literature, Jason Wright's 'SETI in 2020' and Huston & Wright's 'SETI in 2021' cover 75 relevant papers published in 2020, and 98 published in 2021, respectively.

Gaia is not directly related to most of these ideas, searches, and philosophical considerations. But the search for Dyson spheres is already making use of the Gaia data in a very fundamental way.

IN SOME OF THE earliest discussions of SETI, Soviet astronomer Nikolai Kardashev developed the idea of the 'Kardashev scale' as a method of measuring a civilisation's level of technological advancement, based on the amount of energy it is able to use (Kardashev 1964). The classification rests on the premise that any civilisation's energy needs grow continuously with time.

On this Kardashev scale, a Type I civilisation is one that can harness *all* the energy that reaches its home planet from its parent star. For Earth, this value is around 2×10^{17} W, around 10 000 times higher than that presently consumed on Earth, some 2×10^{13} W.

A Type II civilisation is one that has developed to the point that it requires, and can actually consume, most of the total energy emitted by its parent star. And a Type III civilisation requires, and is able to capture, 'all' the energy emitted by its host galaxy.

Assuming a growth rate of 1% per year, Kardashev estimated that it would take humanity 3200 years to reach Type II, and 5800 years to reach Type III. The aim of such a classification was to guide the search for extraterrestrial civilisations, on the assumption (for example) that a fraction of the energy used by each type is assigned to communicate with other civilisations, for which a very substantial energy source is required.

Without going into further details of the whys and hows, I will focus here on what is often considered as one possible manifestation of a Kardashev Type II civilisation, viz. the presence of a 'Dyson sphere' around a planet's host star.

A DYSON SPHERE is a (hypothetical) megastructure that encompasses a star, and which captures a significant fraction of its emitted energy. The concept attempts to explain how a space-faring civilisation would meet its energy requirements once this exceed what can be generated from the home planet's resources alone. Because only a tiny fraction of a star's energy emissions naturally reaches the surface of any orbiting planet, building structures encircling a star would enable a civilisation to harvest substantially more energy.

The idea was popularised by physicist Freeman Dyson (1923–2020) in his paper 'Search for Artificial Stellar Sources of Infrared Radiation' (Dyson, 1960). He speculated that such structures would be the logical consequence of the escalating energy needs of a technological civilisation, and would be a necessity for its long-term survival.

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A FAIRLY EXTENSIVE literature has grown up around this topic, with various suggested hypotheses as to their detailed structural form, including complete or partial shells, rings, and nets (e.g. Wright, 2020).

The relevant point for efforts to detect such structures is that they would alter the light emitted from the star system through absorption and re-radiation, typically resulting in increased *infrared* radiation in the system's emission spectrum. And if the fraction of starlight so affected was significant, the resulting spectral anomalies could be detected over interstellar distances.

Notwithstanding the immense theoretical and practical difficulties involved in their construction, various searches for Dyson spheres, through identification of a star's modified spectrum, have been carried out. Dyson himself argued that the waste heat of the 'energy metabolism' of this extraterrestrial technology would likely be detectable at $10\ \mu\text{m}$, and that a search of the sky at mid-infrared wavelengths would be worthwhile.

PRACTICAL SEARCHES began with the launch of IRAS in 1983, creating the first mid-infrared sky survey with plausible sensitivity. Progressive (unsuccessful) searches were then made by Slysh (1985), Timofeev et al. (2000), Jugaku & Nishimura (2004), and Carrigan (2009).

Subsequently, Arnold (2005) suggested using Kepler to identify transiting megastructures; Teodorani (2014) described the use of Spitzer as a more sensitive probe for infrared excesses; Wright et al. (2014) proposed using the WISE survey to search for Dyson spheres, and Chen & Garrett (2021) used the LOFAR Two-metre Sky Survey (LoTSS) to search for more extreme Type III civilisations.

The discovery of Boyajian's star in 2015 (essay #98) raised early (but subsequently retracted) speculation that the first Dyson sphere may have been discovered (Wright et al. 2016; Wright & Sigurdsson 2016).

IN ALL this work, a continuing difficulty has been to distinguish anomalous Galactic stars from the far more ubiquitous extragalactic infrared (AGN) sources.

And this is where Gaia is contributing: instead of searching for sources with an infrared *excess*, underluminous stars (due to the 'missing' luminosity intercepted by the Dyson sphere) can be identified as a result of their discordant trigonometric and spectroscopic parallaxes (Zackrisson et al. 2015; Wright et al. 2016).

A first application of this approach, using Gaia DR1, has been reported by Zackrisson et al. (2018). As these authors note, with later Gaia data releases, both trigonometric and spectroscopic distance estimates can be obtained from the Gaia data, but in this early analysis, they combined the parallax distances provided by the Tycho-Gaia Astrometric Solution (TGAS) with spectrophotometric distances from Data Release 5 of the ground-based radial velocity survey RAVE.

Candidate Dyson spheres can then also be tested through a comparison of predicted and observed fluxes at mid- and far-infrared wavelengths from space telescopes including IRAS, WISE and Herschel.

Of the 230 000 objects in common between Gaia DR1 and RAVE DR5, they focused on the main-sequence FGK dwarfs, for which current stellar models are expected to produce reliable results. They were left with just 6 outliers, of which TYC 6111-1162-1 was considered to be the most appropriate for further investigation.

For this object, they finally adopted the spectrophotometric parallax listed by RAVE as 4.51 ± 0.8 mas, corresponding to a distance 222_{-35}^{+50} pc, while Gaia DR1 gives a trigonometric parallax 8.72 ± 0.53 mas, implying a distance almost a factor two smaller.

Interpreted as a partial Dyson sphere, it would correspond to a fractional star coverage of 0.77, and a dimming of the host star by around 1.6 mag at optical and near-infrared wavelengths.

Any excitement about the possible discovery of a Dyson sphere was, however, short-lived. A footnote to the article reports that Gaia DR2, released while the paper was under review, confirms that the Gaia DR1 parallax was indeed somewhat preliminary, replacing it with a significantly smaller DR2 parallax of 5.75 ± 0.17 mas. And the astrometric solution may have been further affected by an unseen binary companion, which will become clearer from later data releases.

DESPITE ANOTHER FAILED SEARCH, the power of the method has nonetheless been validated. And future results based on Gaia DR3 should represent another major step forward: in numbers of objects, improved astrometric solutions, identification of binary companions, and by providing both trigonometric and spectroscopic distances from the same global data set.

Other complications remain: one effect that could give rise to spurious Dyson-sphere candidates is grey dust, i.e. line-of-sight material that obscures starlight without causing significant spectral reddening.

SEARCHES FOR ALIEN civilisations are clearly in their infancy, and further ideas along the above lines have recently been detailed (e.g. Haqq-Misra et al. 2022; Huston et al. 2022). And still more exotic approaches to the detection of advanced alien civilisations are being examined, amongst them the proposal to detect signatures of 'star-lifting' as a means of extending the main-sequence lifetime of a host star (Scoggins et al. 2022).

Meanwhile the importance of searching for *both* bio- and techno-signatures, especially in the context of understanding the longevity of alien civilisations, has been emphasised by Wright et al. (2022). I will return to the issue of what non-detections of either might be telling us about our place in the Universe in my next essay.